

FINITE ELEMENT MULTI-SCALE MODELING OF THE FAILURE MECHANISMS IN A 3D WOVEN COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

The progressive degradation of complex textile composites is a significant topic for assessing the durability of these engineering structures. The damage mechanisms observed at the mesoscopic scale – *i.e.* where the yarns are considered as homogeneous - induce variations of macroscopic mechanical parameters such as the stress at failure. This work deals with the link between local stress/strain and the applied load at the macroscopic scale thanks to multi-scale finite element analysis. The noxiousness of broken yarns depending on their number is investigated with regard to the decrease in the stress at failure of the textile composite.

2 Experimental Evidences

The composite material under investigation is a 2.5D angle interlock woven fabric [1-2]. The matrix, the warp and the weft yarns are respectively made of polyvinylchloride (PVC), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polyamide 66 (PA66). A significant decrease in the stress at failure of the textile composite was evidenced on a degraded sample subjected to cyclic bending in service. To better understand the cause of this degradation, experimental investigations at macroscopic and mesoscopic scales were performed.

2.1 Tensile Tests Results

Tensile tests on two kinds of sample were carried out: on the textile composite laminate and on the warp yarn. The measured stresses at failure were respectively 100MPa and 600MPa. The ratio between the local stress at failure (at mesoscopic scale) and the macroscopic one - here equal to 6 - is introduced as a critical stress concentration coefficient. It will be assumed as a key parameter for

the woven composite. Indeed, it depends on the materials, the architecture and the characteristic dimensions of the components.

2.2 Composite Material Architecture

Non destructive X-ray tomography technique was used to inspect the microstructures. Figure 1 shows a reconstructed image of the initial microstructure. The weft and warp yarns can clearly be identified. Additionally, the observations revealed manufacturing defects such as porosity, microcracks networks in the matrix and pieces of naked (debonded) yarns. In the matrix, traces of fillers were also observed.

2.3 Damage Mechanisms

Fig. 2 illustrates a tomographic volume (2.5 mm x 4.9 mm x 7.8 mm) obtained from a degraded sample. At the macroscopic scale, regularly spaced transverse cracks were observed on both faces of the composite material. Two transverse cracks can clearly be evidenced on the PVC matrix at the top face. In addition, the warp yarn located in the upper face of the composite, just under the cracked skin is clearly broken. This breakage occurred on the peak position of the undulation. The fracture surfaces of these broken yarns were oriented perpendicularly to the axis of the warp direction. The cross section corresponding to the warp yarn fracture surface will be investigated in the numerical analysis.

3 Numerical Simulations

3.1 Finite Element Modelling

The following calculations were made using the Finite Element Method (FEM). Linear elastic behaviors were considered. The matrix and the yarns were respectively assumed to be isotropic and orthotropic. The local Euler angles within each yarn

were updated during the computation in order to fit to the orthotropic conditions. A 3D periodic cell was determined from the textile composite architecture (fig. 3). The meshes consisted of 591,209 tetrahedral linear elements, with 312,105 degrees of freedom. In the upper part of the mesh (fig. 3), the matrix was removed in order to show the yarns arrangement. To this periodic cell, a uniaxial tensile Static Uniform Boundary Condition (SUBC) following the warp direction was applied. The mean stress $\langle \sigma_{nom} \rangle$ applied at the macroscopic scale, corresponds to the stress at break of the composite material, *i.e.* 100 MPa.

3.2 Local Stress Distribution

The local stress tensor within a particular warp yarn (fig. 4a) was analyzed. Attention is paid on the largest principal stress (σ_{p1}) for which the eigenvector is systematically normal to the cross section all along the curvilinear abscissa (s) of the warp yarn [2]. The diagram in fig. 4 reveals the trend of normalized σ_{p1} respectively along the upper, the central and the bottom lines of the selected warp yarn. The maximum of σ_{p1} is obtained in the external lines, located in both peak positions (maximum curvature). The corresponding cross sections are noted as skin and core sections in fig. 4a.

The maximum σ_{p1} is estimated at 860MPa by the FE simulation, whereas both transverse principal stresses σ_{p2} and σ_{p3} were negligible. Before comparing this value to the stress at break of the warp yarn, a detailed analysis of the stress state is performed. To this end, the stress triaxiality ratio τ is introduced as

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_{p1} + \sigma_{p2} + \sigma_{p3}}{3\sigma_{p1}} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{p1} , σ_{p2} and σ_{p3} are the principal stresses ordered such that $\sigma_{p1} \geq \sigma_{p2} \geq \sigma_{p3}$. This stress triaxiality ratio τ is then plotted in fig. 5 and its value is roughly constant. Especially, where σ_{p1} is maximum, τ is equal to 0.33, due to $\sigma_{p2} = \sigma_{p3} \approx 0$. Therefore, it can be concluded that in the peak of undulation where the maximum largest principal stress is reached, the stress state is uniaxial, similar

to the stress conditions for test to failure of individual yarn.

Now, attention is paid on the distributions of the maximum principal stress within the aforementioned cross sections: skin and core sections (fig. 6a). $\sigma_{p1}/\sigma_{p1}^{max}$ was plotted as a function of the normalized z -position (height) in both sections in fig. 6b. A stress gradient is clearly observed. Higher stresses are encountered in the hollow part of the curved yarn, *that is* diametrically opposed to the peak position of the undulation. The maximum σ_{p1}^{max} value is located at a small distance from the skin of the yarn. It is estimated at around 1000MPa. Figure 7 shows that, again the stress triaxiality ratio is about 0.33 (uniaxial stress state).

By numerically applying the stress at failure to the textile composite structure (100MPa), the local stress σ_{p1}^{max} computed within a warp yarn is higher than its stress at failure experimentally determined (600MPa). The present multi-scale modeling was able to capture that the failure of the textile composite at the macroscopic scale is due to the fracture of a series of warp yarns within the structure.

The stress concentration coefficient defined as:

$$K_{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma_{pl}^{max}}{\langle \sigma_{nom} \rangle} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{pl}^{max} is the local maximum of the largest principal stress within the warp yarn and $\langle \sigma_{nom} \rangle$ is the mean stress applied at the macroscopic scale on the textile composite, in the warp direction. For the present architecture (fig. 3) $K_{\sigma} = 10$, which is higher than the materials critical value of 6 mentioned in section 2.1. K_{σ} can be considered as an optimization criterion for architecture design. Indeed, a good failure property would be obtained by minimizing K_{σ} .

3.3 Load Transfer Consecutive To Warp Yarn Break

The critical value of $\sigma_{p1}^{max} = 1000\text{MPa}$ was utilized to study the load transfer when consecutive yarns were broken. Typically, a first cut is numerically

incorporated in the warp yarn near the skin of the textile composite (fig. 8). By applying the same $\langle \sigma_{nom} \rangle$ to this structure containing a defect, the maximum load transfer occurred at the closest peak position of a surrounding yarn. The maximum σ_{p1} of this nearest unbroken yarn is recorded and the relative load transfer is defined as:

$$\frac{\Delta \sigma_{p1}}{\sigma_{p1}} (\%) = \frac{\sigma_{p1}^{max}(n+1) - \sigma_{p1}^{max}(n)}{\sigma_{p1}^{max}(n)} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

n being the number of broken yarns (n initial value is 0). Eq. (3) is applied to the nearest yarn of the n -th broken yarn. Fig. 8 illustrates a mesh where two consecutive broken yarns were incorporated.

The evolution of $\Delta \sigma_{p1} / \sigma_{p1}$ as a function of the number of broken yarns is depicted in fig. 9. A continuous increase of the stress is observed. This increase in the relative load transfer means that if a first cut of yarn occurs, an avalanche of yarn breaks is likely to appear. The slope of the curve in fig. 9 is a key parameter to control the failure of the textile composite. This slope depends on the arrangement of undulations within the woven composite.

Furthermore, after 4 broken yarns, the increase of $\Delta \sigma_{p1} / \sigma_{p1}$ is of about 10%. By inverting the K_{σ} formula, it can be demonstrated that this increase results in a decrease of the same magnitude in the stress at failure of the woven composite.

4 Conclusion

The damage mechanisms of a 2.5D angle interlock woven fabric was investigated by means of X-Ray tomography inspections on a degraded sample. Multi-scale FE modeling was performed thanks to a 3D periodic cell. The simulation results showed that the largest principal stress was heterogeneous within the warp yarn. The peak value was obtained in the hollow part of the curved warp yarn. The multi-scale modeling showed that the failure of the textile composite at the macroscopic scale is due to the fracture of a series of warp yarns within the structure. The stress concentration coefficient was proposed to constitute an optimization criterion for architecture design purpose. The slope of the load transfer curve as a function of the number of broken yarns was also proposed as a key parameter to

control the propagation of yarn breakage within the textile composite.

References

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Fig. 1. Tomography volume of the initial microstructure of the textile composite

Fig. 2. Tomography volume of a degraded textile composite

Fig. 3. Meshing of the periodic cell

Fig. 4. Normalized maximum principal stress distribution along a warp yarn ($\sigma_{p1}^{max} = 860\text{MPa}$ and $\sigma_{p2} = \sigma_{p3} \approx 0$)

Fig. 5. Stress triaxiality ratio within a warp yarn

Fig. 6. Normalized maximum principal stress distribution across the section of the warp yarn ($\sigma_{p1}^{max} = 860\text{MPa}$)

Fig. 7. Evolution of the stress triaxiality ratio across the section of the warp yarn

Fig. 8. Mesh of the textile composite with two incorporated broken warp yarns

Fig. 9. Load transfer as a function of the number of broken warp yarn